

DESIGN OF AUTOMOTIVE COMPONENTS

WITH ADVANCED COMPOSITES

C. K. H. Dharan
Ford Aerospace & Communications Corporation
Western Development Laboratories Division
3939 Fabian Way
Palo Alto, California 94303

Abstract

Composite materials are used extensively in aerospace applications because of their excellent stiffness and strength-to-weight ratios. Due to recent increased pressures to improve fuel economy, weight savings in automotive applications has become an important area of investigation. Review of the relationship between automobile structural weight savings and fuel consumption, demonstrates how savings can be accomplished by the judicious application of composite materials.

When considering automotive applications, it is important to take into account the additional weight savings which result from secondary weight effects. A materials substitution analysis is conducted for a beam under flexure, a plate, and a tube. This analysis makes it possible to define relative weights for equivalent performance using composite materials. Analysis results are used to define the maximum allowable material cost for cost-effective application. Findings show that through incorporation of the secondary weight savings effects, the impact of the more expensive composite materials cost is significantly decreased.

To illustrate the foregoing analysis, the design of two automotive components - a leaf spring and a drive shaft - is examined. Both components are governed by stiffness and strength requirements. In each case, only substitution of the steel component is attempted. Graphite-epoxy prototypes were built achieving weight savings of 60-70% relative to their steel counterparts. Evaluation of the performance of the graphite-epoxy prototypes indicates that a proper design and process methodology is essential to arrive at a suitable design.

Introduction

Among structural materials, the chief advantage of composite materials lies in their possession of highest specific strengths and moduli. For this reason, composite materials are used extensively in aerospace and high-performance aircraft applications where saving weight is a prime consideration to increase payload capacity. In commercial and industrial applications, composites have had limited use primarily because of high fiber costs. Recent developments, however, are expected to lower these costs significantly as a result of improvements in fiber production technology. One such development is the manufacture of high-quality graphite fiber from a low-cost pitch precursor. In this process, coal tar pitch, in a liquid crystal phase, is spun into fibers in which the required crystalline orientation is maintained during subsequent graphitization.¹⁾ Through the use of low-cost precursor rather than more expensive rayon or polyacrylonitrile (PAN) precursor filaments, graphite fibers are expected to be marketed in the 1980's at less than \$10 per kg and at a multimillion kg/year production rate. Because of increased usage, even PAN-based fibers have decreased in price to a current level of less than \$40/kg.

For automotive applications, composites can be used effectively to reduce weight. As a result of increased energy costs, improvement of fuel economy through vehicle weight reduction has become an important area of investigation. Although significant weight reductions can be achieved by other means, such as by more efficient structural design or through use of high-strength low-alloy steels, the application of advanced composites to automotive components has the potential to produce dramatic reductions in component weight of a magnitude not possible with conventional materials. Weight savings of 40% to 80%, for example, are possible by substituting composites for metals.

This paper reviews how the structural weight saved is related to fuel consumption in automobiles and how the savings can be accomplished by the judicious application of composite materials. A materials substitution analysis is conducted for simple structural geometries such as a beam, a plate, and a tube under torsion. Conventional structural materials and advanced composites are compared for applications governed by stiffness (buckling), ultimate strength, and fatigue strength. To illustrate these results, design and manufacturing considerations for a drive shaft and leaf spring are examined. Both components are governed by stiffness and strength requirements, and in each case, only substitution of the steel component is attempted. That is, the fiber-reinforced part is designed to be interchangeable with the steel part with no additional modifications in the mounting configuration and in design of existing accessory components.

Obviously, this procedure does not allow one to obtain all the secondary weight savings that are possible when weight is reduced in one component. A proper systems approach would be to design an entire vehicle in which all possible weight savings opportunities are exploited and the whole system is evaluated against a conventional vehicle having the same packaging and performance criteria. For the purpose of this design study, however, a part-to-part replacement approach was the only one considered since it was the quickest way to evaluate the substitution of composites in conventional automotive components.

Vehicle Weight Dependence and Fuel Economy

Empirically determined, the relationship between total vehicle weight and fuel consumption (km/l) is shown in Fig. 1. Also shown is the dependence of the reciprocal of the fuel consumption (l/km) on vehicle weight. This is represented by a straight line relationship in which the slope is approximately 10×10^{-5} l/km/kg (2×10^{-5} gal/mi/lb). Thus, reducing the weight of a 2050 kg (4500 lb) vehicle by 450 kg (1000 lb) will result in the saving of 1080 liters (300 gal) of gasoline per year, assuming an annual mileage of 24,000 km (15,000 mi).

Fig. 1. Empirical relationship between fuel consumption (l/km or km/l) and vehicle weight for approximately equal performance.

It is important to understand that the primary weight saved by substituting lighter materials is further augmented by secondary weight reductions in the other vehicle subsystems. Thus, the substitution of a lighter body structure results in smaller brakes, tires, engine, fuel tank, etc, leading to additional weight savings. Only part of the total weight saved, therefore, would be derived from material substitution. This is fortunate with respect to automotive applications of composites, since it reduces the economic impact associated with use of more expensive though lighter materials.

To quantitatively determine secondary weight savings, an analysis of 1975 Ford production cars was conducted by Magee,⁽²⁾ who determined the functional dependence of various subsystem weights on total vehicle weight. The total vehicle weight W can be considered to consist

of a product function weight W_p , which is a function of packaging, performance, and configuration and is independent of weight changes made elsewhere in the vehicle, and a weight W_D , which is dependent on weight changes made elsewhere. Thus,

$$W = W_p + W_D \quad (1)$$

A simple linear relationship was found to adequately represent W_D for each subsystem.⁽²⁾ As a first approximation,

$$W_D = kW + C \quad (2)$$

where k and C are constants. Figure 2 shows how the weight of one subsystem (brakes) varies as a function of vehicle weight. A least squares fit resulted in the following equation for the brakes subsystem:

$$W_D (\text{Brakes}) = 0.041 W + 0.55 \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2. Brakes subsystem weight vs vehicle curb weight.⁽²⁾

When this is done for all subsystems, and the results added, the values of k and C in Eq.(2) are obtained. Substituting Eq.(2) in (1),

$$W = W_p + kW + C$$

or

$$W = mW_p + C_1 \quad (4)$$

where

$$m = (1 - k)^{-1} \quad (5)$$

Magee obtained m to have a value between 2.1 and 2.6 for the vehicles considered. That is, every kg saved in primary weight results in the saving of an additional 1.1 to 1.6 kg in secondary weight. This is an important result. It provides a quantitative basis for the large additional weight savings possible when composite materials are substituted for conventional automotive steels.

Several assumptions are implied in the foregoing analysis, the most important one being that subsystem weight dependence on total-vehicle weight is a continuous function. In reality, subsystems exist discretely and therefore down-sizing which results from primary weight savings, can only be done at the next available subsystem level. This effect will change the secondary factor. Another assumption is that the slope k , for each subsystem, remains constant when secondary weight savings are being calculated. This would not be true if drastic design changes or materials substitution in a particular subsystem would cause a change in its dependence on total-vehicle weight. For example, the substitution of composite materials for the bumper subsystem will result in a new weight dependence relationship. In calculating its subsequent contribution to the secondary weight factor when a materials substitution is made in another subsystem, one must use the new weight dependence relationship. For the analysis to accurately reflect potential secondary weight savings, therefore, updated versions of the weight dependence relationship, Eq. (2), must be used. The result would be a decrease in the secondary weight factor as light weight materials substitution proceeds in each subsystem.

From the foregoing, it is evident that each local effort at weight reduction results in an overall weight savings that is more than double the primary weight saved. This means that judicious use of composite materials in selected subsystems may pay off - even though these materials are more expensive than conventional materials - because the large magnitude of the local weight savings results in an even greater amount of weight savings elsewhere in the vehicle.

Materials Substitution with Composite Materials

To evaluate the relative weight savings possible when composites are substituted for metals, a materials substitution analysis was carried out for a variety of geometries under different constraints. For the purposes of this paper, only three cases will be discussed: beams of fixed width for equal bending moment and stiffness, plates of fixed width and length for equal longitudinal buckling load, and tubes of fixed diameter for equal torsional moment.

The performance criterion that has to be met (for example, stiffness) defines the material and geometric parameters. In the simplest case, by using additional constraints, all but one of the geometric parameters are usually eliminated resulting in a relation which is used with the weight equation to obtain a final equation describing the functional dependence of the weight on the density and material

properties. For example, for a beam, the flexural stiffness k is proportional to EI where E is the flexural modulus and I , the moment of inertia of the beam:

$$k \propto EI \quad (6)$$

For beams of equal width,

$$k \propto Ed^3 \quad (7)$$

where d is the depth of the beam. The weight (per unit length) of the constant width beam is:

$$W \propto \rho d \quad (8)$$

where ρ is the weight density of the material. From Eqs. (7) and (8)

$$W \propto \rho E^{-1/3} \quad (9)$$

Similarly, for equal-width beams capable of sustaining the same bending moment,

$$W \propto \rho \sigma^{-1/2} \quad (10)$$

where σ is the maximum fiber stress in the beam. Equations (9) and (10) were used to calculate the relative weights of beams of equal width for the same stiffness, ultimate strength, and fatigue strength for various materials. The results are shown in Table I, in which all the weights are normalized with respect to spring steel. Also shown are the values assumed for the modulus, ultimate strength, and fatigue strength. For the composites, these values correspond to laminates in which all fiber orientation is not solely in the longitudinal direction. Some cross-plying is included since, in actual practice, it would be required to provide adequate transverse strength. The effect is to reduce the longitudinal properties of the composite and increase its relative weight. However, a more realistic measure of actual weight savings is obtained rather than the optimistic values derived from solely longitudinally oriented laminate properties.

Table I shows that for stiffness-controlled and fatigue-controlled applications, graphite-epoxy provides the greatest possible weight savings. In ultimate strength applications, the weight saved is only slightly better than that obtainable with glass-epoxy.

The relative magnitudes of the weights derived for equal stiffness, ultimate strength, and fatigue strength with respect to spring steel (in Table I) are also important. For both graphite and glass-epoxy composites, the relative weight required to meet the stiffness requirement is larger than that required for ultimate strength or fatigue strength.

Table I. Relative weights for beams of fixed width for equal flexural stiffness, flexural strength and flexural fatigue strength.

Material	Density (Relative to Steel)	Relative Weights		
		Stiffness $\rho E^{-1/3}$	Strength $\rho \sigma_u^{-1/2}$	Fatigue $\rho \sigma_e^{-1/2}$
Steel	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
		E = 195 GPa	$\sigma_u = 1240$ MPa	$\sigma_e = 345$ MPa
Graphite-epoxy	0.20	0.22	0.23	0.13
		E = 140 GPa	$\sigma_u = 980$ MPa	$\sigma_e = 785$ MPa
Glass-epoxy	0.25	0.47	0.30	0.32
		E = 30 GPa	$\sigma_u = 840$ MPa	$\sigma_e = 210$ MPa
Aluminum	0.35	0.50	0.57	0.51
		E = 70 GPa	$\sigma_u = 470$ MPa	$\sigma_e = 165$ MPa

This means that a beam designed to the stiffness requirement will be overdesigned with respect to strength. In the case of aluminum, however, when the stiffness is matched, the beam will not meet the fatigue or ultimate strength requirements. In order to match the ultimate strength (relative weight = 0.57), the aluminum beam will be stiffer than required (relative weight = 0.50).

Table II shows a similar analysis for buckling of a fixed length plate and a given load. For this case:

$$W \propto \rho E^{-2/5} \tag{11}$$

Table II. Relative weights for elastic buckling of plates of fixed length for an equal buckling load.

Material	Relative Density	Relative weights for plates of fixed length and equal buckling load ($\rho E^{-2/5}$)
Steel	1.00	1.00
		E = 195 G Pa
Graphite-epoxy [0/90] _{ns}	0.20	0.31
		E = 65 G Pa
Glass-epoxy [0/90] _{ns}	0.25	0.62
		E = 20 G Pa
Aluminum	0.35	0.52
		E = 70 G Pa

For a cylindrical tube of uniform wall thickness, designed to transmit a specified torque for a given diameter,

$$W \propto \rho \tau^{-1} \quad (12)$$

where τ is the shear strength of the material. The relative weights are shown in Table III.

Table III. Relative weight for thin-walled tubes of fixed diameter for an equal torsional load.

Material	Relative Density	Relative weight for thin-walled tubes of given diameter and torque ($\rho \tau_y^{-1}$)
Steel (low carbon)	1.00	1.00
		$\tau_y = 170 \text{ MPa}$
Graphite-epoxy [(0/90) _m (±45) _n] _s	0.20	0.28
		$\tau_y = 125 \text{ MPa}$
Glass-epoxy [(0/90) _m (±45) _n] _s	0.25	0.33
		$\tau_y = 130 \text{ MPa}$
Aluminum	0.35	0.41
		$\tau_y = 145 \text{ MPa}$

Composite Materials Cost Analysis

In order to provide a basis for cost tradeoffs for various materials substitutions, it is interesting to determine the composite materials cost requirement for a given application.

Let W_c be the relative weight of the composite component (normalized with respect to steel) for a particular application. For a stiffness-controlled beam of fixed width, for example,

$$W_c = \frac{\rho_c E_c^{-1/3}}{\rho_s E_s^{-1/3}}$$

where subscripts c and s refer to the composite and steel respectively.

The weight saved (with respect to steel) equals $1 - W_c$. If C_c and C_s are the costs per kg of the composite and steel respectively, then the cost penalty as a result of the substitution = $W_c C_c - C_s$. The cost penalty per kg of weight saved is then given by:

$$C_p \geq \frac{W_c C_c - C_s}{1 - W_c} \quad (13)$$

Rearranging Eq. (13),

$$C_c \leq \frac{C_s}{W_c} + \left(\frac{1-W_c}{W_c}\right) C_p \quad (14)$$

Equation (14) provides a relation between the maximum allowable composite material cost per kg, C_c for a given material cost penalty per kg saved, C_p . For no allowable cost penalty, Eq. (14) states that the composite material cost per kg should be less than $(1/W_c)$ times the steel cost per kg. Thus, the smaller the relative weight W_c , the greater the allowable cost of the composite.

Equation (13) is shown plotted in Fig. 3 for graphite-epoxy for a range of costs per kg for spring steel. For spring steel at \$1.50/kg, the price of graphite-epoxy should be less than \$6.80/kg if no cost penalty is allowed. For an estimated price of \$10.00/kg for graphite-epoxy, a cost penalty of \$0.90/kg is entailed.

Effect of Secondary Weight Savings

When secondary weight savings are taken into account, Eqs. (13) and (14) are modified by the addition of the secondary weight factor. The total weight saved (primary plus secondary) is now $m(1-W_c)$ where m is defined in Eq. (5). The cost penalty is then given by:

$$C_p \geq \frac{W_c C_c - m C_s}{m(1-W_c)} \quad (15)$$

It is assumed here that the cost per kg of the secondary weight saved is the same as the primary steel. Equation (15) is also shown plotted in Fig. 3 for $m = 2.4$. The price of graphite-epoxy in a stiffness-controlled application, now, need only be less than \$16.40/kg (spring steel = \$1.50 per kg) for a zero cost penalty substitution. This figure is substantially larger than the value calculated without secondary weight savings, and is above most high-volume material price projections for graphite-epoxy.

The foregoing analysis illustrates the importance of taking into account secondary weight savings in order to determine the actual cost penalty incurred when substituting a higher cost composite material. Only the stiffness-controlled application of graphite-epoxy was analyzed here. The same analysis should be conducted for the other parameters and for other materials in a tradeoff study - taking care to note that in a specific application, the constraints will, in general, be different from the ones assumed here and will change the relative weight and secondary weight factors.

In order to determine feasibility, a design study was also conducted and prototypes of an automotive drive shaft and leaf spring were built using graphite-epoxy. The purpose was to determine the weight savings possible and whether the components would pass all the testing requirements specified for their steel counterparts.

Fig. 3. Material cost penalty per kg saved (C_p) vs composite material cost per kg (C_c) for beams of fixed width and equal stiffness for various spring steel costs per kg. (The dashed lines show the same relationship when secondary weight savings are taken into account.)

The Graphite-Epoxy Leaf Spring

The spring chosen for study was a truck auxiliary tapered single-leaf steel spring. The choice was influenced by its simple geometry (no spring eyes) which makes it suitable for a preliminary evaluation study such as the present one. Steel spring specifications are given below:

- Spring rate = 360 kN/m (2050 lb/in)
- Rated load = 10.2 kN (2300 lb)
- Fatigue loading requirement: 50,000 cycles from -1.2 cm to 2.5 cm about the rated load position
- Mass = 7.4 kg (16.2 lb weight)

The graphite-epoxy replacement spring was designed to match the spring rate (equal EI) and the width of the steel spring, and to meet its fatigue loading requirement. The response of the material to cyclic loading was determined for both flexural and interlaminar shear fatigue loading using the fixtures described elsewhere.^(3,4) These tests were critical in defining the margins of safety for the graphite-epoxy design in the fatigue loading environment noted above. They were also useful in providing a basis for the prediction of the probable mode of failure of the composite spring.

In determining the final configuration, it was decided that a constant cross-section spring would be more desirable from manufacturing considerations instead of a replica of the steel tapered design. To build the graphite-epoxy prototypes, a matched-metal die was constructed. Graphite-epoxy tape prepreg (with Union Carbide's Thornel 300 graphite fiber) was hand laid up and compression molded at 120°C at 0.7 MPa pressure. The final prototype is shown with the steel spring in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Steel leaf spring (single-leaf, tapered) and graphite-epoxy prototype leaf spring.

Fig. 5. Test setup on fatigue machine for fatigue testing graphite-epoxy prototype leaf spring.

The graphite-epoxy prototype springs were subjected to a series of laboratory tests including fatigue and impact loading. The setup for the fatigue test is shown in Fig. 5. The spring was mounted to the actuator of a servo-hydraulic fatigue machine and cyclically loaded against cams mounted on a beam attached to the load frame of the test machine. The cyclic loading rate (over full jounce to rebound) was maintained at 0.2 Hz under load control. The stiffness was monitored continuously during the test by using high-speed dual strip-chart recorders which recorded the cyclic load and displacement profiles measured by the load cell and LVDT transducers. A decrease in the stiffness by 5% was arbitrarily defined as failure.

The graphite-epoxy prototype successfully passed the fatigue requirement of 50,000 cycles (full jounce to rebound) and was cycled for an additional 50,000 cycles with no indication of failure. The results for the graphite-epoxy spring are given below:

- Spring rate = 372 kN/m (2124 lb/in)
- Fatigue loading (with no failure): 100,000 cycles from -1.2 cm to 2.5 cm about the rated load position
- Mass = 2.2 kg (4.8 lb weight)

The weight relative to the steel spring is larger than that predicted in Table I for a stiffness-controlled application. This is because of the constant cross-section design of the graphite-epoxy spring which is less efficient than the tapered leaf steel design. In spite of this, the weight savings of 70% is substantial.

The Graphite-Epoxy Drive Shaft

The parameters that govern automotive drive shaft design are: first-bending-mode resonant frequency, fatigue torque, and impact torque. For the steel drive shaft, the requirements to be met were:

Maximum torque = 1080 N-m (800 ft-lb)

Fatigue torque = ± 750 N-m (± 550 ft-lb)

First-bending-mode resonant frequency > 4100 r/min

The principal objectives of the graphite-epoxy drive shaft design were to (a) possess satisfactory torsional fatigue strength, (b) withstand occasional impact torsional loads, and (c) possess high flexural stiffness in order to meet the resonant frequency requirement.

A three-piece design, in which a graphite-epoxy tube is bonded to two steel yokes, was chosen as a suitable configuration for prototype construction. The problem thus reduces to one that involves design of the composite tube and steel-to-composite torsional bond joint.

For thin-wall tubes, the torsional stress is

$$\tau = \frac{T}{2\pi R^2 t} \quad (16)$$

where T is the torque, R the tube radius, and t the wall thickness. The first-bending-mode resonant frequency for simply supported shafts is

$$f = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{\pi^2}{\ell^2} \left(\frac{E_L I}{m} \right)^{1/2} \quad (17)$$

where ℓ is the length between supports, E_L the longitudinal (axial) laminate modulus, I the moment of inertia, and m the mass per unit length of the shaft. In general, for hybrid composites,

$$m = \sum_i m_i \cong 2\pi R \sum_i \rho_i t_i \quad (18)$$

where ρ_i is the density of the i th ply of thickness t_i . For thin-walled tubes:

$$E_L I = \pi R^3 E_L t \quad (19)$$

Equation (17) is, therefore,

$$f = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(\frac{\pi^2}{\ell^2} \right) R \left(\frac{E_L t}{2\sum \rho_i t_i} \right)^{1/2} \quad (20)$$

Equation (20) indicates the interesting result that, for a homogeneous, isotropic shaft (such as steel) of a given length, the first-bending-mode resonant frequency is directly proportional to the shaft diameter and is independent of the wall thickness. It is also proportional to the square root of the specific modulus (E/ρ), making drive shafts a particularly relevant application for composite materials.

Fig. 6. Graphite-epoxy prototype automobile drive shaft.

Equations (16) and (20) were used with laminate plate theory analysis and laminate point stress analysis to obtain a design which met the requirements with adequate margins of safety. The analyses were complemented by coupon testing and torsion tests. Figure 6 shows a prototype shaft of the final design. The prototype shafts were manufactured using graphite-epoxy prepreg on a high-speed rolling table machine.

The graphite drive shaft prototypes passed all the specified tests, meeting or exceeding the requirements noted earlier for the steel shaft. The masses of the two shafts are:

1. Graphite-epoxy shaft (excluding yokes) = 1.09 kg (2.4 lb weight), and
2. Steel shaft (excluding yokes) = 3.36 kg (7.4 lb weight).

Conclusion

The results of composite materials substitution for a variety of structural geometries quantitatively show the dramatic weight reductions possible. For beams of fixed width, for example, a graphite-epoxy beam weighs only 22% of the weight of an equivalent steel beam for the same flexural stiffness. When considering automotive applications of composites, it is important to take into account the additional weight savings resulting from secondary weight effects. A lighter bumper system designed with composite materials, for example, produces additional weight savings in the other vehicle subsystems because of lighter wheels, suspensions, body structure, etc. When all these savings are added, the total weight savings obtained is more than double the initial weight savings obtained from composite materials substitution. This effect makes the substitution of lighter though expensive materials more palatable, and increases the maximum allowed cost of the substituting material for a given cost penalty per kg saved.

An analysis of the material cost level necessary for zero cost penalty per kg substitution shows that for beams of fixed width and equal stiffness, the maximum allowed cost per kg for graphite-epoxy increases from \$6.80/kg to \$16.40/kg when secondary weight savings are taken into account (spring steel assumed at \$1.50/kg). This is greater than most high-volume price projections for graphite fiber. For simplicity, it is assumed that the cost per kg of the secondary weight saved is the same as the primary steel cost. In a more accurate analysis, the functional dependence of the cost of each subsystem should also be incorporated. This preliminary analysis, however, illustrates the importance of a systems approach to materials substitution in automotive applications to appreciate fully the extent of the weight savings possible.

Two automotive components were designed and prototypes were built with graphite-epoxy: a leaf spring and drive shaft. Both prototypes passed all the tests specified for their steel counterparts. Weight savings of 68% for the drive shaft (excluding yokes) and 70% for the leaf spring were achieved. Evaluation of the performance of the graphite-epoxy prototypes indicates that a proper design and process methodology is necessary to arrive at a final design. This includes stress analysis using laminate plate and shell theory, materials studies to determine the composite materials response under monotonic, cyclic loading and component testing. It should be emphasized that long-term vehicle tests were not conducted, nor were the effects of humidity, temperature, or stone damage (simulating the environment the component would see in actual use) investigated. The effect of stone damage on flexural

fatigue of pultruded graphite-polyester was shown in an earlier study to be small because of the notch-insensitivity of graphite-epoxy.(5) However, the tests were conducted on laboratory flexural fatigue samples and not on actual components. In addition, in actual use, the possible synergistic effect of all the environmental components acting simultaneously must be investigated.

A final note: In the materials substitution cost analysis described in this paper, only single-fiber component composites were considered. Multifiber or hybrid composites offer additional potential to decrease material cost by combining small quantities of an expensive fiber such as graphite with less expensive fibers such as glass. Hybridizing is especially useful where different multidirectional properties are needed in a laminate; for example, when flexural stiffness is required in one direction and strength in another. For such cases, graphite fibers may be advantageously employed in the direction requiring high stiffness, while less expensive glass fibers may be used in the direction requiring strength, with little difference in relative component weight, and at a much lower cost. Materials substitution analyses with hybrid composites are part of an ongoing study and will be reported on at a later date.

Acknowledgments

The author wishes to thank Mr. H. L. Hillesland, Materials Engineering Department (FACC), and Drs. N. A. Gjostein and C. L. Magee, Research Staff (Ford Motor Company), for valuable discussions on composite materials substitution. The author is also grateful to Dr. B. Eckstein of Union Carbide's Carbon Products Division for helpful suggestions on processing graphite-epoxy. Technical support was provided by Mr. J. T. Rucker and Mr. T. M. Galvin, Materials Engineering Department (FACC).

References

1. H. F. Volk, "High Performance Carbon Fibers and Cloth from Pitch," Proc 1975 International Conference on Composite Materials, The Metallurgical Society of AIME, New York (1976).
2. C. L. Magee, "Weight Interaction - Part I: 1975 Ford Cars," Ford Motor Company Research Staff Report No. SR-75-105 (1975).
3. C. K. H. Dharan, "Fatigue Failure Mechanisms in Pultruded Graphite-Polyester Composites," in Failure Modes in Composites II, eds. J. N. Fleck and R. L. Mehan, The Metallurgical Society of AIME, New York (1974).
4. C. K. H. Dharan, "Interlaminar Shear Fatigue of Pultruded Graphite Fiber - Polyester Composites," J. Materials Science (in press).
5. C. K. H. Dharan and P. Beardmore, "The Resistance of Graphite Fiber - Reinforced Composites to Impacts," in Failure Modes in Composites III, The Metallurgical Society of AIME, New York (1976).